

Phase Shift of $\exp[i \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle dx]$ for Bound Quantum Systems Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 20, 2020

In a previous note, we suggested that the change (d/dx) in the relative conditional probability at x i.e. $\exp(ikx)$ of a photon or free quantum particle (from deBroglie's picture) may be applied to a bound state average relative conditional probability $W(x)$ (the wavefunction) so that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle dx)$ where $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i d \ln(W) / dx$. We went on to argue that $- d/dx d/dx W / W = \langle pp \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ which may be linked to a conservation of energy equation i.e. the Schrodinger equation. In this note, we extend these ideas to the relativistic Klein-Gordon case and also examine further statistical properties which follow, including the result that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i .5 \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle dx + i .5 dx \langle p \text{ ave at } x+dx \rangle)$ to second order in dx . It seems that the variance of p is directly linked to terms which appear in an energy conservation equation and so one may immediately write such an equation without the necessity of statistical equations such as the continuity, Fokker-Planck or telegraph's equation.

Phase Shift and Average Momentum at x in a Bound System

Photons have been described by $\exp(ikx)$ for a long time and de Broglie suggested a similar form for quantum objects such as electrons i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ is a statistical result because its modulus is 1 everywhere suggesting a particle has equal probability to be at any x . In classical statistical mechanics, one would assign a constant real number to describe this probability, but in quantum mechanics particles remember their path and interactions along the way as demonstrated in interference experiments. Thus, describing the probability by a constant is only part of the picture i.e. $P(x)$. We argue that there is a conditional probability picture with $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ so $\exp(ipx)$ plays an important role. $W(x)$, the wavefunction, is a sum ("or" situation) of relative conditional probabilities i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

$\exp(i p (x+dx)) = \exp(ipx) \exp(i p dx)$ for both a photon and free quantum particle. In a previous note (part 1), we suggested that the bound state wavefunction should behave in a similar manner i.e. $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(- \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle dx)$ ((1)) where $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln(W)$ ((2)). This result follows from a first order expansion. Out of curiosity, one may consider a second order expansion i.e.

$$W(x+dx) = \exp[i \ln[W(x+dx)/i]] = W(x) [1 + i \{-i d \ln W/dx dx - 1/2 d/dx d/dx \ln(W)\} + \dots] \quad ((3))$$

Given that: $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln W$, $d/dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i d/dx d/dx \ln W$ so

$\langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle + dx (-i) d/dx d/dx \ln W$ ((3)) then becomes:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp[i (\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle .5dx + \langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle .5 dx)] \quad ((4))$$

In other words, to second order in dx , $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(idx \text{ Average of } (\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \text{ and } \langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle))$.

This accounts for the fact that $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ changes with x unlike the constant p in $\exp(ipx)$.

Relativistic Considerations

$\exp(ipx)$ holds for both nonrelativistic and relativistic cases, but momentum is $m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in the latter and $m_0 v$ in the former. Thus, we argue that the above ideas should be relevant for both nonrelativistic and relativistic cases (at least for the Klein-Gordon situation) because $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i d \ln W / dx$ for the Schrodinger case and also for the Klein-Gordon case if one ignores the factor of 2 in: $-i [W(KG)^* d/dx W(KG) + W(KG) d/dx W^*(KG)]$.

For both cases: $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i/dx \ln W$ suggests that $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$. This also follows by using $W = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which should hold for both nonrelativistic and relativistic cases. $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$, however, may be utilized in both nonrelativistic and relativistic energy conservation equations i.e.

Nonrelativistic case: $1/2m (-d/dx d/dx W/W) + V(x) = E$

Relativistic case with $V(x)=0$: $-d/dx d/dx W / W + m_0^*m_0 = E^*E$ ((5))

In the literature (1,2), a continuity equation is usually used to develop the nonrelativistic Schrodinger case and another equation (e.g. the telegraph equation) the relativistic one. We suggest both follow from the same idea, namely the behaviour of $W(x)$ as one changes from x to $x+dx$ i.e. the creation of the phase $\exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle)$.

Statistical Considerations

It seems that the form $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln(W)$ ((6)) is related to some statistical properties in the quantum bound problem. If there exists an average p (momentum) at x , there should also be a variance. We argue that ((6)) is equivalent to $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Mathematically, this is a Fourier series, but that does not guarantee that $\exp(ipx) a(p)$ is a probability. The idea that $W(x)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ change in a similar manner as $x \rightarrow x+dx$, however, seems to support that idea that $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ i.e. establish a conditional probability at x . If this is the case, then $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$ and:

$-i d/dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = \text{Var}(p \text{ at } x)$ ((7))

The average value of p at x changes with x as its variance. As shown in the first section, this ensures that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i dx \{ \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle + \langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle \} / 2)$. In other words, to second order in dx , $\langle p \rangle$ is represented by the average of $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle$ as one moves from x to $x+dx$. (To first order, one has $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.) This is an interesting consequence. Even more interesting, however, is that $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ is related to the kinetic energy in the nonrelativistic case and pp in the relativistic. Thus, $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ in $\text{Var}(p \text{ at } x)$ which is linked to the sum of relative conditional probabilities at x i.e. $W(x)$, may now be linked directly to an energy conservation

equation as noted in the previous section. No stochastic statistical equations such as a telegraph equation, continuity equation or Fokker-Planck equation is needed in such a situation.

As a final consideration, consider:

$$\text{Var}(p \text{ at } x+dx) = \langle pp \text{ at } x+dx \rangle - \{ \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle + i dx \text{ Var}(p \text{ at } x) \}^2$$

$$\text{approx} = 2m (\text{Average KE at } x+dx) - \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle - i dx 2 \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \{ 2m(E-V(x)) - \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle \} \quad ((8))$$

Again, one may see that average energy terms are intertwined with statistical variances.

Note: $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln(W)$, but W is real for a bound state, so $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ must be purely imaginary which seems to be fine because there is no overall translation of the system as in the case of $\exp(ipx)$ for which $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle dx)$ ((9)) i.e. that the relative conditional probability at x for a bound state change as $\exp(ipx)$ for a photon or free quantum particle leads to: $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln(W)$ which in turn leads to $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W / W$. This may be used in both the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases to establish the time-dependent Schrodinger and Klein-Gordon equations by using energy conservation. We also note that ((9)) holds to first order in dx , but in second order $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ is replaced with $.5(\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle + \langle p \text{ at } x+dx \rangle)$ because $\langle p \rangle$ changes with x . We show that this is equivalent to $-id/dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = \text{Var}(p \text{ at } x)$. Finally, we consider how $\text{Var}(p \text{ at } x)$ changes with x i.e calculate $\text{Var}(p \text{ at } x+dx)$ and show that it contains terms related to average energy. In this approach, it seems one may link statistical quantities to average energy quantities without using traditional stochastic equations such as the continuity, Fokker-Planck or telegraph's equations.

References

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